

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report
Responsible Partner: VEGEPOLYS VALLEY**

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“Let’s Build our SFSC!” Event Validation Report – France

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY for the organisation and validation of **the “Let’s build our SFSC” event in France organised on the 24th of February 2023**. This event was an online brokerage and networking event, aiming to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agroBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agri-food sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the “*Construisons nos circuits-courts en France*” (Let’s build our SFSC in France).
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

Our event “Let’s build out SFSC” in France has been organised on the 24th of February 2023. The event started at 10 A.M by a presentation of the agroBRIDGES project and some of the tools developed for the project’s toolbox.

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
Activity #1	Presentation of agroBRIDGES and some tools developed and instructions how to use the Brella platform	10:00 – 10:20	Members of VEGEPOLYS VALLEY	Breakout Rooms
Activity #2	Presentation of the different structures connected	10:20 – 10:30	N/A	Breakout Rooms
Activity #3	One-to-one meetings	10:30 – 18:00	N/A	Meetings

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

For the organisation of the event, two main persons were involved: the first one working on the back office of Brella (the matchmaking online platform) to understand how it works and set up the different breakout room, and the second person to program the event and set up the list of invitees. These two persons worked together on the presentation of agroBRIDGES and some tools to open the event.

A third person was involved to disseminate widely about the event into our channels and networks of communication.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Functioning of the platform Brella	1	Understanding of how the platform Brella works	In-house	0.5 person days
Creation of the event	1	Set up on the Brella platform	In-house	0.5 person days
Checking of the operation of the event	2	Tool test	In-house	0.25 person days
Communication on the event	3	Invite interesting people, communicate on the social networks, relaunch of invitations	In-house	1.75 person days
Organisation of the opening of the event	1	Preparation of a PowerPoint	In-house	0.25 person days
Opening of the event	2	Presentation, animation	In-house	0.25 person days

2.3 Event material

To realize the event, we did a publication on LinkedIn (see figure 1). One invitation has been sent via e-mail (see Figure 2) and two remembers for the event and the subscription were also sent.

We personalized the event on the Brella platform by adding the agroBRIDGES logo and an image illustrating a vegetable referring to SFSC (see Figure 3).

During the event, a presentation was developed to introduce the project and few of the tools developed for the agroBRIDGES toolbox to inform attendees (see Figure 4).

Figure 1: Publication realised on LinkedIn to announce the event

Figure 2: Invitation mail sent to the event

Rencontrons-nous pour construire nos circuits courts le 24/02 !
À Maiti ROUSSET

Construisons nos circuits-courts en France : rencontrons-nous !

Dans le cadre du projet européen [AgroBridges](#), et dans la suite du [Prix des héros locaux](#), le pôle VEGETOLYS VALLEY vous invite à participer à un événement de rencontres professionnelles des circuits-courts alimentaires le 24 février prochain.

Le concept ?

Producteur, distributeur, restauration collective, collectivité locale... Vous êtes un acteur des circuits courts alimentaires, ou vous souhaitez le devenir : inscrivez-vous à notre événement pour rentrer en contact et prendre rendez-vous avec votre futur client, partenaire, prestataire...

Le programme :

- 10h ouverture de l'événement avec une présentation rapide du projet agroBridges (rdv sur l'onglet Breakout room)
- Jusqu'à la fin de journée, planifiez vos rendez-vous en visio avec les participants à l'événement pour développer vos partenariats et votre marché.

Nous resterons disponibles pour tout besoin de mise en relation ultérieure.

Vous souhaitez présenter votre projet et/ou votre besoin ? Contactez-nous pour organiser une session parallèle !

INSCRIPTION

pour réserver dès à présent vos rencontres !

Belle journée à vous,
Bien cordialement,

Maiti BOUSSIT
Chargée de mission
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6 rue Emile Duclaux
63000 SAINT BEAUZIRE

Figure 3: Presentation of the platform for the event

Figure 4: Extract from presentation slides

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

For the organisation of our “Local Heroes Award” one month earlier, we had created a big list of contacts related to SFSC.

To communicate about “Let’s build out SFSC in France”, we used and completed this list with actors potentially interested to work in SFSC (for example road hauliers) or who have a contact network potentially interested in this approach (for instance chambers of Agriculture).

We send personal e-mail invitations to 195 structures (one month before the event) and we did 2 e-mails or telephone reminders (2 weeks and 1 week before the event).

We also published on LinkedIn an announcement and a call to subscribe to the event 15 days before the event.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

During the event, participants submitted 11 meeting requests out of which 4 were accepted, 6 left pending and 1 cancelled/rejected.

Most of the people connected to the opening of the matchmaking platform knew each other. It was a pleasure to see that the SFSC network was already active and connected before organizing this type of event. However, it limited the success of the event as they didn't plan so many meetings during the day. The ones who were connected are the ones who are all the time invested in different actions and projects. It is hard to mobilize the others as they already participated to many events before this one. One participant failed to connect to the opening of the event, it was then a digital or connexion issue related.

The meetings that stayed pending are mainly due to people or structures that already knew each other or some that did not find any interest in exchanging with the person who had requested the exchange.

The screenshot below illustrates an extract of the presentation delivered online to participants.

Figure 5: Review of matchmaking activities

3.2 Event participation

15 people subscribed to participate to the event and 11 of them have been present on 28/02/2023.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	2
Start-up (valorization of agricultural co-products)	2
e-commerce, online platform	2
Territorial representatives	3
Mutualisation	1
Total	11

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	11		0		0	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Did you find this event helpful to meet professionals and businesses you can collaborate with?	0	2	0	9	0	0
Do you think that this event helped you see Short Food Supply Chains as a promising business alternative?	0	0	4	5	2	0

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Did you find the matching and booking of one-to-one meetings with other people useful to identify and negotiate collaborations?	0	1	0	0	10	0
Was the event useful in supporting you to find interesting opportunities to collaborate with other businesses for the development of Short Food Supply Chains?	0	0	3	1	6	1
Question	Monthly or more	3-4 times per year	Twice per year	1 time per year	Never	Prefer not to answer
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	0	2	0	9	0	0
Total	11	5	4	20	25	1

Most of the feedbacks we had from the people participating to this event were related to the lack of registered participants as well as the diversity of profiles represented.

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The organization of that kind of event can be interesting however to had not enough registrations for the event to be relevant.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

If we organize again a similar event, we should focus on one particular theme (eg: the market gardening sector).

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

Despite the strong communication on the event, we had very few registered participants and for an event like this to be of interest, you need to have lots of choices of contacts to discover, which was not our case.

Moreover, some interested people couldn't participate during the event because it took place during school holidays for a region of France. As mentioned earlier in the document, most of the participants already knew each other, which did not help to make interesting meeting sessions. The event wasn't enough focused on a specific challenge according to some participants, a more related topic challenge could be appropriate to interest actors.

5. Conclusions

The event wasn't as successful as we expected. We conclude that In France, the SFSC network is already well connected and doesn't need help on this aspect.

Nevertheless, we presented other agroBRIDGES tools that were of interest for the participants, so we know it is better to focus on these ones for the French ecosystem.